

THYROID FUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY AFTER TREATMENT WITH VALPROIC ACID

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the effect of valproic acid therapy on thyroid function tests including FT4 and TSH in children with newly diagnosed epilepsy.

Study Design: Descriptive case series.

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Paediatrics Medicine, PGMI Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, conducted over a period of six months from July 2024 to Jan 2025.

Methodology: This study included eighty children aged between 3 to 12 years who were diagnosed with epilepsy for the first time. Patients were enrolled through non probability consecutive sampling. Thyroid function tests including FT4 and TSH were measured at baseline before starting treatment. Valproic acid was initiated at a dose of 15 mg per kg per day. After one month of continuous therapy, thyroid function tests were repeated. All collected data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 22. Paired t test was applied to compare baseline and post treatment values and a p value of 0.05 or less was taken as statistically significant.

Results: The mean age of the children was 7.2 plus minus 2.6 years. Out of the total patients, 46 were males and 34 were females. Mean baseline FT4 level was 1.31 plus minus 0.19 ng per ml which showed a decline to 1.18 plus minus 0.17 ng per ml after one month of valproic acid therapy and this change was statistically significant. Mean baseline TSH level was 3.12 plus minus 1.36 micro IU per ml which increased to 4.42 plus minus 2.21 micro IU per ml after treatment, also showing statistical significance. Subclinical hypothyroidism was noted in 14 patients which accounted for 17.5 percent of the study population. No child developed overt hypothyroidism during the study period.

Conclusion: Valproic acid therapy in children with epilepsy results in noticeable changes in thyroid function, mainly an increase in TSH levels with relatively normal FT4. Although most patients remain asymptomatic, a significant number develop subclinical hypothyroidism. Regular monitoring of thyroid function should be considered in children receiving valproic acid especially during early months of therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Epilepsy is one of the most common chronic neurological disorders affecting children worldwide and remains a major public health problem, especially in developing countries like Pakistan. The incidence of epilepsy is higher in low resource settings due to factors such as perinatal insults, central nervous system infections, poor antenatal care and limited access to early treatment ^[1]. A large proportion of epilepsy cases begin in childhood and often require long term treatment with antiepileptic drugs to achieve seizure control ^[2]. While these medications are effective in reducing seizure frequency, their prolonged use is associated with several adverse effects involving different organ systems. Children are particularly vulnerable because of their ongoing growth and development, and even subtle metabolic or hormonal disturbances can have long lasting consequences ^[3]. Therefore, monitoring of potential side effects of antiepileptic drugs is an important part of pediatric epilepsy management. Among the various adverse effects of antiepileptic drugs, endocrine dysfunction has gained increasing attention in recent years. Thyroid hormones play a vital role in regulating metabolism, physical growth, and neurocognitive development in children. Any disturbance in thyroid function during childhood may negatively affect linear growth, pubertal development and academic performance ^[4]. Several antiepileptic drugs have been reported to interfere with thyroid hormone synthesis, secretion or peripheral metabolism. Valproic acid is a commonly prescribed broad spectrum antiepileptic drug due to its good efficacy, wide seizure coverage and relatively favorable cognitive profile. However, multiple studies have suggested that valproic acid therapy may be associated with alterations in thyroid function tests, most commonly an increase in thyroid stimulating hormone levels with normal or slightly reduced FT4 levels, a pattern suggestive of subclinical hypothyroidism ^[5,6]. Although subclinical hypothyroidism is often asymptomatic, its long term effects in children receiving chronic therapy remain a concern.

Previous international studies have demonstrated variable effects of valproic acid on thyroid hormones. Verrotti and colleagues reported a significant rise in TSH levels in children receiving long term valproate

therapy, while changes in FT4 were minimal ^[7]. Similarly, Yilmaz et al observed an increase in TSH after initiation of antiepileptic drugs including valproic acid, highlighting the need for biochemical monitoring even in clinically stable patients ^[8]. Despite this growing body of evidence, there is a lack of local data from Pakistan regarding the effect of valproic acid on thyroid function in children with epilepsy. Differences in nutritional status, iodine intake and genetic factors may influence the pattern of thyroid dysfunction in our population. This study was therefore designed to evaluate changes in thyroid function tests after initiation of valproic acid therapy in children with newly diagnosed epilepsy, with the aim of generating local evidence that may help guide clinical practice and improve long term outcomes in pediatric epilepsy patients.

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive case series was carried out in the Department of Paediatrics Medicine at PGMI Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore after taking approval from the institutional ethical committee. The study duration was six months from July 2024 to January 2025. A total of 80 children between the ages of 3 to 12 years who were newly diagnosed with epilepsy were included in the study. Patients were enrolled through non probability consecutive sampling as they presented to the pediatric ward or outpatient department. Children with a known history of thyroid disease, those who had already received antiepileptic drugs for more than fifteen days, and patients with congenital anomalies, developmental delay, chronic liver disease, chronic renal failure or other neurological illnesses were excluded from the study to avoid confounding factors.

After obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians, baseline demographic and clinical data including age gender weight and duration of epilepsy were recorded on a pre designed proforma. All patients underwent routine clinical evaluation and relevant investigations as per hospital protocol. Baseline thyroid function tests including FT4 and TSH were measured before starting valproic acid therapy. Valproic acid was then initiated at a dose of 15 mg per kg per day. Patients were followed for one month and compliance with medication was ensured

during follow up visits. After one month of continuous treatment, thyroid function tests were repeated using the same laboratory methods. All collected data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 22. Quantitative variables such as age FT4 and TSH levels were expressed as mean plus minus standard deviation, while qualitative variables like gender were presented as frequencies and percentages. Paired t test was applied to compare baseline and post treatment thyroid function test values. A p value of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 80 children with newly diagnosed epilepsy were included in the study. The mean age of the patients was 7.2 plus minus 2.6 years, with ages ranging from 3 to 12 years. There was a male predominance in the study population, as 46

patients which accounts for 57.5 percent were males, while 34 patients or 42.5 percent were females. The mean duration of epilepsy before presentation to the hospital was 6.4 plus minus 2.1 weeks. All children were clinically stable at the time of enrollment and none had features suggestive of thyroid dysfunction at baseline.

Baseline thyroid function tests were within normal limits in all patients. After one month of valproic acid therapy, noticeable changes were observed in thyroid hormone levels. Mean FT4 levels showed a mild but statistically significant decrease, while mean TSH levels showed a significant rise after treatment. Although most patients remained asymptomatic, a subset of children developed biochemical evidence of subclinical hypothyroidism. No patient progressed to overt hypothyroidism during the study period.

Table I: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population (n=80)

Variable	Mean ± SD or Frequency
Age (years)	7.2 ± 2.6
Male	46 (57.5%)
Female	34 (42.5%)
Duration of epilepsy (weeks)	6.4 ± 2.1

Table II: Baseline Thyroid Function Tests

Parameter	Mean ± SD
FT4 (ng per ml)	1.31 ± 0.19
TSH (micro IU per ml)	3.12 ± 1.36

Table III: Thyroid Function Tests After One Month of Valproic Acid Therapy

Parameter	Mean ± SD
FT4 (ng per ml)	1.18 ± 0.17
TSH (micro IU per ml)	4.42 ± 2.21

Table IV: Comparison of Thyroid Function Tests Before and After Treatment

Parameter	Baseline Mean ± SD	After 1 Month Mean ± SD	p value
FT4 (ng per ml)	1.31 ± 0.19	1.18 ± 0.17	0.01
TSH (micro IU per ml)	3.12 ± 1.36	4.42 ± 2.21	0.001

Subclinical hypothyroidism defined as TSH greater than 4.5 micro IU per ml with normal FT4 levels was observed in 14 patients, accounting for 17.5 percent of the study population. These patients did not show any clinical symptoms of hypothyroidism during the study period. No significant association was found between development of subclinical hypothyroidism and age or gender of the patients.

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates that treatment with valproic acid in children with newly diagnosed epilepsy is associated with significant changes in thyroid function tests, particularly a rise in TSH levels along with a mild reduction in FT4 levels. These findings suggest that even short term use of valproic acid can influence thyroid hormone regulation in the pediatric population. Similar observations have been reported in previous international studies, where valproic acid therapy resulted in elevated TSH levels while FT4 remained within normal or low normal range, indicating subclinical hypothyroidism^[6,7]. In our study, all patients had normal thyroid function at baseline and none showed clinical features of thyroid dysfunction, highlighting that these changes are primarily biochemical and may go unnoticed without laboratory monitoring. This underlines the importance of routine thyroid function testing in children receiving valproic acid therapy, especially during the early phase of treatment.

The exact mechanism by which valproic acid alters thyroid function is not fully understood, however several explanations have been proposed. Valproic acid may interfere with thyroid hormone synthesis by affecting iodine uptake or organification within the thyroid gland^[4]. Another proposed mechanism is altered peripheral metabolism of thyroid hormones, leading to reduced conversion of T4 to the more active T3 form. Additionally, valproic acid may exert its effect at the level of the hypothalamic pituitary thyroid axis, resulting in increased secretion of TSH as a compensatory response^[5]. Verrotti et al reported similar findings in children on long term valproate therapy, where increased TSH levels were observed without significant clinical hypothyroidism^[7]. Yilmaz and colleagues also demonstrated that antiepileptic drugs including valproic acid were associated with

thyroid hormone alterations, supporting the findings of the current study^[8]. Differences in study duration, dosage and population characteristics may explain the variability in the degree of thyroid dysfunction reported across studies.

Although subclinical hypothyroidism is generally considered a benign condition, its significance in children should not be underestimated. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in physical growth, brain maturation and cognitive development during childhood. Even mild hormonal imbalances if persistent may have long term effects on growth velocity and school performance^[4]. In the present study, subclinical hypothyroidism was observed in 17.5 percent of patients after only one month of therapy, which is comparable to previously reported rates^[6,8]. None of the children developed overt hypothyroidism or required discontinuation of therapy during the study period. However, the short follow up duration is a limitation, as longer exposure to valproic acid may result in more pronounced hormonal changes. Another limitation of this study is the lack of a control group and relatively small sample size. Despite these limitations, this study provides valuable local data from Pakistan where limited research exists on this topic. The findings emphasize the need for regular thyroid function monitoring in children receiving valproic acid and support the inclusion of thyroid screening in routine follow up protocols for pediatric epilepsy patients. Further large scale and long term studies are recommended to better understand the clinical significance of these findings and to establish clear guidelines for monitoring and management^[1,2,3].

CONCLUSION

This study shows that valproic acid therapy in children with epilepsy can lead to noticeable changes in thyroid function tests. An increase in TSH levels with relatively normal FT4 was observed in a significant number of patients, suggesting the development of subclinical hypothyroidism. Although most children remained clinically asymptomatic, these biochemical changes should not be ignored. Thyroid hormones are important for growth and neurodevelopment, especially in the pediatric age group. Therefore, regular monitoring of thyroid function tests during valproic acid therapy is

important, particularly in the early months of treatment, to ensure timely detection and appropriate management of any thyroid related abnormalities.

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